

SYNTHESIS IN THE ACRIDINE SERIES. PART IX. N-SUBSTITUTED 3-METHOXY-8-CHLORO-9-AMINOACRIDINES

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Synthesis of several N-substituted-3-methoxy-8-chloro-9-aminoacridines is described.

The work in earlier papers has now been extended to include N-substituents of 3-methoxy-8-chloro-9-aminoacridines.

Condensation of N-m-chlorophenylbenzimidazole chloride with methyl 4-methoxy-salicylate gave N-m-chlorophenylbenzimidazole-5-methoxy-2'-carbomethoxyphenyl ether (I), which on heating to 270° isomerised to methyl N-benzoyl-5'-chloro-5-methoxy-diphenylamine-2-carboxylate (IV). Treatment of (IV) with excess of alkali gave 5'-chlorodiphenylamine-5-methoxy-2-carboxylic acid (III). Condensation of (III) with POCl₃ gave N-m-chlorophenylbenzimidazole-5-methoxy-2'-chloro-8-chloro-9-aminoacridine (II, m.p. 168-170°). Treatment of (IV) with OH⁻ gave 5'-chlorodiphenylamine-5-methoxy-2-carboxylic acid (III). Condensation of (V) with POCl₃ gave N-m-chlorophenylbenzimidazole-5-methoxy-2'-chloro-8-chloro-9-aminoacridine (VI, m.p. 216-17°). Condensation of (VII) with POCl₃ gave N-m-chlorophenylbenzimidazole-5-methoxy-2'-chloro-8-chloro-9-aminoacridine (VIII, m.p. 194-95°). Condensation of (IX) with POCl₃ gave N-m-chlorophenylbenzimidazole-5-methoxy-2'-chloro-8-chloro-9-aminoacridine (VIII, m.p. 194-95°).

The diphenylamine acid (X) on ring-closure with phosphoryl chloride can give a mixture of the two acridines, *i.e.* 3-methoxy-6,9-dichloroacridine (VI) and 3-methoxy-8,9-dichloroacridine (II), according as the ring-closure takes place in position 6' or 2'. Experimentally, however, only one component (m.p. 168-70°) was obtainable in high yield (80%) from the reaction mixture. The reason why structure (II) was assigned to this product will become clear from the following discussion.

According to Albert *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 88; 1942, 377) the component which is obtained in lower yield and has a higher melting point of the two isomers, must be regarded as the 3-substituted compound. There are, however, numerous exceptions to this, and actually the amount of the two isomers is dependent to a very great extent on the nature of the 5'-substituents. Thus, Lehmsstedt and Schrader (*Ber.*, 1937, 70 B, 838) found that whereas 5'-nitrodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid gave on ring-closure 75-80% of the 1-nitroacridone, the corresponding 5'-methyl analogue gave only 18% of the methylacridone. It is well known that during electrophilic substitution of negatively substituted aromatic compounds, the percentage of the *ortho* component formed is always much greater than the *para* isomer. This is because the interference of the electronegative group resonance with the transition state of substitution is greater for the *para* substitution than for the *ortho* substitution. In the case of an electropositive substituent at position-5', the *ortho:para* ratio is also known to be dependent on the nature of the entrant substituent, though in majority of these cases, there is a greater preponderance of the *para* isomer over the *ortho* one. Probably the activation of the aromatic ring caused by the electropositive group is greater for the *para* position than for the *ortho* position, on account of the extended conjugation in the former case. We have thus found that during the ring-closure of 4'-methoxy-6-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (VII) the major component was 3-methoxy-7,9-dichloroacridine (VIII, m.p. 194-95°), whose structure was confirmed by its unequivocal synthesis from 4'-chlorodiphenylamine-5-methoxy-2-carboxylic acid (IX) where (VIII) was to be the sole product of the reaction. In the case of 5'-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid the ring-closure has been found to take place invariably on 6'-position in preference to the 2'-position. Shah, Kshatriya, Patel and Nargund (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1946, 15A, Part III, 42) claimed that the ring-closure of 5'-chlorodiphenylamine-4-methoxy-2-carboxylic acid (X) yielded only 2-methoxy-6,9-dichloroacridine. In our hands a product of m.p. 178-80° could be isolated from the reaction mixture. This could not have been the 6-isomer, which is known to melt at 162° and, therefore, must correspond to structure (XI). Such was also the experience of Dauben (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 2420). Recently Dauben and Hodgson (*ibid.*, 1950, 72, 3479)

have provided conclusive evidence to this effect. From analogy with these examples, a tentative, though very likely, structure for the acridine (m.p. 168-70°) obtained by the ring-closure of (III) must be considered as represented by (II). Similarly the major product (m.p. 216-17°) obtained by ring-closure of (V) by analogy with ring-closure of the corresponding 4-chloro isomer (VII) must be formulated as 3-methoxy-6:9-dichloroacridine (VI). It is hoped to provide a definite proof for the structures (II) and (VI) in a subsequent communication.

3-Methoxy-8:9-dichloroacridine (II), thus obtained, was further condensed with various amines to give the desired 9-N-substituents.

EXPERIMENTAL.

N-m-Chlorophenylbenzimidino-5'-methoxy-2'-carbomethoxyphenyl ether was prepared in a manner analogous to that described for the corresponding *p*-chloro isomer (vide Part VII, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 459). It was crystallised from 98% ethanol in white prisms, m.p. 112-13°, yield 83%. It was not possible to carry out a nitrogen analysis, as the compound gave off nitrogen with explosive violence, when heated with cupric oxide above its melting point.

Methyl-N-benzoyl-5'-chloro-5-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylate was also prepared according to procedures described earlier. It was crystallised from absolute ethanol in white glistening clusters, m.p. 113-14°. In this case too, the nitrogen analysis could not be recorded.

5'-Chlorodiphenylamine-5-methoxy-2-carboxylic acid was crystallised from 95% alcohol in slightly brownish needles, m.p. 167-68°. (Found: N, 5.34. $C_{14}H_{12}O_2NCl$ requires N, 5.04 per cent). The corresponding *acid chloride*, prepared by treatment of the acid with phosphorus pentachloride in absolute petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°), was obtained as yellow needles, m.p. 112° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.60. $C_{14}H_{12}O_2NCl_2$ requires N, 4.74 per cent).

3-Methoxy-8:9-dichloroacridine was prepared by treatment of the above diphenylamine acid with phosphoryl chloride in the usual way. After one crystallisation from dry benzene, the acridine was obtained as yellow micro needles, m.p. 168-70°. The melting point could not be raised by recrystallisation, yield 80%. (Found: N, 5.15. $C_{14}H_8ONCl_2$ requires N, 5.03 per cent).

3-Methoxy-8-chloroacridone.—3-Methoxy-8:9-dichloroacridine (1 g.) was refluxed with 50 c.c. of 5% hydrochloric acid for about 4 hours, when the yellow acridine slowly changed to the white acridone. The product was filtered off and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as a white powdery mass which did not melt till 310°. (Found: N, 5.26. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2NCl$ requires N, 5.39 per cent).

5'-Methoxydiphenylamine-5-chloro-2-carboxylic Acid.—Potassium metal (1 atom, 4.6 g.) was dissolved in 30 c.c. of methanol and dry 2:4-dichlorobenzoic acid (one mol., 23 g.) was added followed by *m*-anisidine (1.5 mols., 20.4 g.), copper powder (0.1 g.) and

Cu_2Cl_2 (0.1 g.); 30 c.c. of isoamyl alcohol were then added and the reaction mixture as heated in an oil-bath at 140° for 2-3 hours. Methyl alcohol was allowed to evaporate off from a short air-condenser. Excess of isoamyl alcohol was then distilled off and the last traces removed by passing steam. The residue after being made acidic to Congo red was crushed to a green powder. It was extracted with potassium bicarbonate (charcoal) and decomposed with hydrochloric acid yielding a voluminous yellow mass. After drying, it was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in bright greenish yellow needles, m.p. $189-90^\circ$, yield 80%. (Found: N, 5.01. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}$ requires N, 5.04 per cent). The acid chloride was crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. $80-81^\circ$. (Found: N, 4.95. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}_2$ requires N, 4.74 per cent).

3-Methoxy-6:9-dichloroacridine.—The ring-closure of the above diphenylamine acid was effected by treatment with phosphoryl chloride. The product was crystallised from dry benzene as a greenish yellow substance, m.p. $200^\circ-207^\circ$. Two more crystallisations raised the melting point to $216-17^\circ$, which could not be improved by further recrystallisations; yield of the pure component was 25-35%. (Found: N, 4.92. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{ONCl}_2$ requires N, 5.03 per cent).

5'-Methoxy-4-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid was obtained from 2:5-dichlorobenzoic acid and *m*-anisidine, according to the conditions described earlier. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as greenish yellow needles, m.p. $189-90^\circ$. (Found: N, 5.01. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{NCl}$ requires N, 5.04 per cent). The acid chloride was crystallised from petroleum ether as golden yellow plates, m.p. 88° . (Found: N, 4.71. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}_2$ requires N, 4.74 per cent).

3-Methoxy-7:9-dichloroacridine.—The ring-closure of the above diphenylamine carboxylic acid was effected in the usual manner. The product was crystallised from benzene as a yellow powder, m.p. $180-86^\circ$. Three more crystallisations gave a sharp melting product, m.p. $195-96^\circ$, which could not be raised by further recrystallisations. This product is identical with that obtained by the ring-closure of 4'-chlorodiphenylamine-4-methoxy-2-carboxylic acid, as described in Part VII (*loc. cit.*). A mixed melting point determination of the two samples did not show any depression.

5'-Chlorodiphenylamine-4-methoxy-2-carboxylic acid was obtained by the condensation of 2-bromo-5-methoxybenzoic acid and *m*-chloroaniline in 65% yield, under conditions similar to those described in Part I (this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 466). It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow needles, m.p. $181-82^\circ$. (Found: N, 4.85. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{NCl}$ requires N, 5.04 per cent). The acid chloride was crystallised from light petroleum ether as golden yellow needles, m.p. 93° . (Found: N, 4.83. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}_2$ requires N, 4.74 per cent).

2-Methoxy-8:9-dichloroacridine.—The above diphenylamine acid on treatment with phosphoryl chloride gave a mixture of two acridines which melted between 144° and 154° . Repeated crystallisations from anhydrous benzene gave 15-20% of a pure component with a sharp melting point, $178-80^\circ$. Dauben (*loc. cit.*) for the same compound has reported a m.p. 182° .

3-Methoxy-8-chloro-9-(δ -diethylaminobutyl)-aminoacridine was prepared by the condensation of 3-methoxy-8:9-dichloroacridine and δ -diethylaminobutylamine in the

usual way. The base was characterised by the formation of its dihydrobromide which was crystallised from a mixture of absolute ethanol and ether as a yellow powder, m.p. 212-14°. (Found: N, 7.77. $C_{22}H_{28}ON_3Cl \cdot 2HBr$ requires N, 7.67 per cent).

3-Methoxy-8-chloro-9-(ε-diethylaminoamyl)-aminoacridine was characterised by its picrate, which was crystallised from a mixture of ethanol and acetone as a yellow powder, m.p. 196-98°. [Found: N, 14.50. $C_{23}H_{30}ON_3Cl \cdot 2(C_6H_3N_3O_7)$ requires N, 14.68 per cent].

3-Methoxy-8-chloro-9-(di-n-propylaminopropyl)-aminoacridine.—The dihydrobromide was twice crystallised from an ethanol-ether mixture as a yellow powder, m.p. 209-211°. (Found: 7.98. $C_{21}H_{28}ON_3Cl \cdot 2HBr$ requires N, 7.88 per cent).

3-Methoxy-8-chloro-9-(di-n-butylaminopropyl)-aminoacridine.—The dipicrate was crystallised from alcohol-acetone mixture, m.p. 171-73°. [Found: N, 14.0. $C_{25}H_{34}ON_3Cl \cdot 2(C_6H_3O_7N_3)$ requires N, 14.22 per cent].

3-Methoxy-8-chloro-9-(di-n-amylaminopropyl)-aminoacridine was also characterised by its dipicrate, which was crystallised from an alcohol-acetone mixture as yellow tiny crystals, m.p. 152-54°. [Found: N, 14.49. $C_{27}H_{37}ON_3Cl \cdot 2(C_6H_3O_7N_3)$ requires N, 13.80 per cent].

3-Methoxy-8-chloro-9-(di-n-propylaminobutyl)-aminoacridine.—The dipicrate was crystallised from a mixture of ethanol and acetone as a yellow powder, m.p. 217-19°. [Found: N, 14.23. $C_{24}H_{32}ON_3Cl \cdot 2(C_6H_3O_7N_3)$ requires N, 14.46 per cent].

3-Methoxy-8-chloro-9-(di-n-butylaminobutyl)-aminoacridine.—The dipicrate was crystallised from alcohol-acetone mixture as yellow needles, m.p. 205-207°. [Found: N, 13.63. $C_{26}H_{36}ON_3Cl \cdot 2(C_6H_3O_7N_3)$ requires N, 14.0 per cent].

3-Methoxy-8-chloro-9-(di-n-amylaminobutyl)-aminoacridine.—The dipicrate, m.p. 136-38°. [Found: N, 13.18. $C_{28}H_{40}ON_3Cl \cdot 2(C_6H_3O_7N_3)$ requires N, 13.58 per cent].

3-Methoxy-8-chloro-9-(γ-piperidinopropyl)-aminoacridine.—The dihydrochloride was twice crystallised from absolute ethanol, m.p. 242°. (Found: N, 9.08. $C_{22}H_{26}ON_3Cl \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 9.20 per cent).

3-Methoxy-8-chloro-9-(δ-piperidinobutyl)-aminoacridine.—The dihydrochloride was twice crystallised from a mixture of absolute ethanol and ether, m.p. 219-21°. (Found: N, 8.82. $C_{23}H_{28}ON_3Cl \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 8.92 per cent).

3-Methoxy-8-chloro-9-aminoacridine was prepared in the usual manner from 3-methoxy-8:9-dichloroacridine. It was crystallised from a mixture of ethanol and acetone in yellow glistening needles, m.p. 188-90°. (Found: N, 10.70. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 10.83 per cent).